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BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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Promoting SMART agricultural WATER management in Bosnia and Herzegovina - “SMARTWATER” project

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Abstract

Promoting SMART agricultural WATER management in Bosnia and Herzegovina — “SMARTWATER” is a HORIZON 2020 project granted by European Commission and coordinated by the University of Banja Luka. The main objective is to reinforce networking, research and science and technology cooperation capacities of the University of Banja Luka (UNI-BL), the University of Sarajevo (UNSA) and other connected BiH institutions, in the field of sustainable agricultural water management and to increase their competency and fund rising skills for a successful participation in the European Union (EU) Research Programs. In this context, the project promoted the twinning with the EU institutions including Mediterranean Agronomic Institute of Bari (CIHEAM-IAMB), Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC), Instituto Superior de Agronomia (ISA), SYSMAN PROGETTI & SERVIZI SRL (SYS). SMARTWATER project will develop a large set of joint activities promoting networking, joint experimental fields, research cooperation and the exchange of knowledge and experts. The focus will be on the application of smart technologies (cloud-based and remote sensing) in agricultural water management, the optimization of the water–energy–food nexus, climate change impacts and adaptation measures. Moreover, the project will provide technical assistance and expertise to improve the research and innovation capacities of BiH institutions and to delineate adequate research strategies and policies for the future. Hence, the project will boost the S&T capacity through a series of capacity building actions focusing mainly on the early-stage researchers. These include

advanced training courses, participation in a joint MSc program, summer schools and hands-on workshops on R&I funding. A modern scientific strategy for stepping up and stimulating scientific excellence and innovation capacity will be outlined following a multi-stakeholder participatory approach.

Key words: Water, Management, Smart, Technologies, BiH